

A STUDY ON THE BIAXIAL FATIGUE OF E-GLASS/EPOXY LAMINATES UNDER NORMAL AND SHEAR LOADINGS

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Keywords: Biaxial fatigue, Laminates, Arcan specimens

ABSTRACT

Fatigue behavior of fiber reinforced polymer laminates under uniaxial loading has received much more attention compared to biaxial loading primarily due to the intricacy and difficulty in designing and conducting biaxial tests. This paper will present biaxial fatigue data of $[0/90/0_5/0]_s$ E-glass/epoxy laminates under a combination of normal and shear loadings. A butterfly-shaped Arcan specimen was developed and used for fatigue testing. The specimen design was optimized using finite element analysis. Two different specimen configurations were considered, longitudinal specimens with 0° fiber orientation in the outer layers and transverse specimens with 90° fiber orientation in the outer layers. A variety of combinations of shear and normal stresses were created by changing the orientation of the specimen with respect to the loading direction. In the present study, fatigue tests were conducted with longitudinal and transverse specimens at five different loading angles, namely 0° , 30° , 45° , 60° and 90° . By varying the loading angle, it was possible to create load combinations that ranged from pure tension, mixed tension-shear and pure shear. The maximum fatigue load in each case was a percentage of the load at knee determined in static biaxial loading. This paper will present biaxial fatigue life diagrams of the laminate and make a comparative analysis of fatigue performance under various combinations of normal and shear loadings.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced polymers (FRP) are used in many different structural forms and applications in aircraft, space, automotive, marine and multiple other industries. Their use has increased in the last few decades owing specifically to their high strength-to-density and high modulus-to-density ratios. A recent example of this increased usage of FRP can be seen in the Boeing 787 Dreamliner which uses FRP, principally carbon fiber reinforced epoxy, in 50% of its primary structure. The application of FRP in automotive structures is also on the rise. Due to the recently increased Corporate Average Fuel Economy (CAFE) regulations in the United States and similar regulations in other countries, automakers worldwide are developing materials, processes and test procedures in the field of FRP which may allow them to move away from conventional metallic materials, especially steel. With this increasing usage of FRP, it has become increasingly important to study and understand their fatigue behavior under different loading conditions, since fatigue properties play a vital role in the design of many structures and structural components.

Fatigue behavior of FRP under uniaxial loading has received much more attention compared to biaxial loading [1], primarily due to the intricacy in designing and conducting biaxial tests. Majority of the test data corresponding to biaxial static and fatigue performance of FRP that exist in the open literature have come mainly from three types of test specimens [2], which are 1) off-axis specimens, 2) cruciform specimens, and 3) thin-walled tubular specimens. Of the three types of test specimens, only

thin-walled tubular specimens can be used to apply a combination of a normal stress and a shear stress. The normal stress is created by the application of either an internal pressure or an axial load and the shear stress is created by the application of a torsional load. Though a tubular specimen has the advantage of allowing multiaxial loading, it has many unique challenges, such as specimen fabrication, working fluid-test material interaction, non-uniform stress distribution through the thickness and the possibility of failure by torsional buckling. The effect of the combination of normal and shear stresses on laminated FRP plates has not been studied in the past. The knowledge of these types of loading is very important since the majority of FRP applications involve laminated plate or shell structures, and in general, the FRP laminates are relatively weak in shear loading.

With this background, this paper will present the fatigue life diagrams of a continuous fiber reinforced polymer laminate under a combination of normal and shear loadings. The test method uses a butterfly-shaped Arcan specimen, which is a modified form of the Arcan specimen originally developed in 1978 by Arcan and his co-workers [3] for determining shear properties of fiber reinforced polymers [4]. The versatility of the Arcan specimen is that it can be utilized for testing materials either under uniaxial normal loading, shear loading or a combination of in-plane normal and shear loadings.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Material

The material used in this study is an E-glass fiber reinforced epoxy flat laminate composed of 15 layers and has a stacking sequence described by $[0/90/0_5/\bar{0}]_s$. One layer from each of the outer surfaces contains fibers in the transverse direction, but the fiber orientation in remaining 13 layers is in the longitudinal direction. The trade name for the material is Scotchply 1002. The Scotchply laminates were originally developed by 3M and is now available by the trade name Cyply 1002 from Read Seal Electric Co. in USA. The nominal fiber volume fraction in the laminate is 64 percent. The longitudinal tensile modulus and strength, as reported by the laminate manufacturer, are 39.3 GPa and 965.3 MPa, respectively.

2.2 Arcan Specimen

The overall dimensions of the butterfly-shaped Arcan specimen used in this study are 50 mm x 75 mm x 3.3 mm (thickness) as shown in Figure 1. The notch radius at the corner of the 90° notch angle is 10 mm. The details of the specimen design are given in Reference [5]. The distance between the notch ends is 23.28 mm; thus the cross-sectional area of the specimen between the notch tips, considered the significant section, is 76.82 mm². The specimen has three 6-mm diameter bolt holes drilled at each end for mounting it to the loading fixture. Two different specimen configurations were prepared for the purposes of testing: 1) the longitudinal specimens in which the 0° layers are perpendicular to the significant section, referred to as '1-2 specimens' and 2) the transverse specimens in which the 0° layers are parallel to the significant section, referred to as '2-1 specimens'. Figure 2 shows a schematic of the 1-2 and 2-1 specimens. In this figure, the 0° layers are represented by the solid lines and the 90° layers are represented by the dotted lines. In the 1-2 specimens, 13 of the 15 layers or 87% of the layers were the 0° layers. Similarly, in the 2-1 specimens 13 of the 15 layers or 87% of the layers were the 90° layers.

Figure 1: Dimensions of butterfly-shaped Arcan specimens used in this study.

Figure 2: (a) 1-2 and (b) 2-1 configuration of the Arcan specimen.

2.3 Tests

Both monotonic tensile and load-controlled cyclic fatigue tests were conducted on an MTS 810 servo-hydraulic test system. The fixture for testing the Arcan specimens is shown in Figure 3 and is described in Reference [5]. The monotonic tensile tests were conducted at a crosshead rate of 2 mm/min. Table 1 and Table 2 show the specimen configurations and loading angles at which the tensile and fatigue performance of the E-glass fiber reinforced epoxy laminate were evaluated.

Loading Angle (°)	Test Configuration	
	1-2	2-1
0	No	Yes
15	Yes	Yes
30	Yes	Yes
45	Yes	Yes
60	Yes	Yes
90	Yes	Yes

Table 1: Specimen configurations and the loading angles used for tensile tests.

Loading Angle (°)	Test Configuration	
	1-2	2-1
0	No	Yes
15	No	No
30	Yes	Yes
45	Yes	Yes
60	Yes	Yes
90	Yes	Yes

Table 2: Specimen configurations and the loading angles used for fatigue tests.

Figure 4 shows a schematic of two loading angles: 90° and 45° . The 90° loading angle subjects the Arcan specimens to shear loads, whereas 45° loading angle subjects the Arcan specimens to equal shear-tensile load combination. It is to be noted that as the loading angle α is increased from 0 to 90° , the shear stress component increases while the normal stress component decreases. In our experiments, the normal stress component for the 1-2 specimens is σ_{11} and for the 2-1 specimens, it is σ_{22} .

All fatigue tests were performed in load-controlled mode at 2 Hz frequency and with an R-ratio (P_{\min}/P_{\max}) of 0.1. The load and crosshead displacement signals were continuously monitored and recorded throughout the tests. The cycle at which the instantaneous stiffness (load divided by crosshead displacement) becomes equal to half the stiffness at 100 cycles was considered as the failure cycle for the material. If a specimen did not fail, the fatigue test was discontinued after a *runout* life of 2×10^6 cycles.

Figure 3: Photograph of an Arcan specimen mounted on the test fixture. The loading angle is denoted by α and is measured from the vertical axis of the loading fixture.

Figure 4: (a) 90° loading angle and (b) 45° loading angle.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Monotonic Tests

Figure 5 and Figure 6 show the monotonic load-displacement diagrams of the 1-2 and 2-1 Arcan specimens, respectively. Though the monotonic performance of the 1-2 specimens is generally higher than that of the 2-1 specimens, it is seen that the monotonic behavior of both specimen configurations is highly dependent on the loading angle. Furthermore, the load carrying capacity of the material decreases

with increasing loading angle whereas the displacement-to-failure increases. Unlike the 2-1 specimens, the 1-2 specimens at loading angles of 45° and higher show a more distinct ‘knee’ load beyond which the load-displacement response changes. Each load-displacement curve starts with a linear segment, which gradually transforms into a non-linear segment as damage appears in the specimen. At the end of the non-linear segment, the load-displacement curve again becomes almost linear until the load starts to drop in random steps. The ‘knee’ load was determined at the intersection of the extrapolated linear segments before and after the non-linear segment. The average knee load and the peak load for each specimen configuration are given in Table 3.

Loading angle	Specimen configuration	Knee load, kN	Peak load, kN
0°	2-1	3.74 ^A	8.40 ^A
15°	1-2	13.07 ^A	22.71 ^A
	2-1	3.40 ^A	7.63 ^A
30°	1-2	8.02 ^B	16.45 ^B
	2-1	2.76 ^B	6.15 ^B
45°	1-2	5.40 ^B	12.67 ^B
	2-1	2.46 ^B	5.31 ^B
60°	1-2	4.45 ^A	10.67 ^A
	2-1	2.44 ^A	4.51 ^A
90°	1-2	3.96 ^B	6.73 ^B
	2-1	2.22 ^B	4.43 ^B

(A) and (B) are average of two and four specimens respectively

Table 3: Knee and peak loads for each monotonic tensile load condition.

Figure 7 shows a comparison of the tensile performances of 1-2 and 2-1 specimens under shear load which was developed at a 90° loading angle. It is seen that the initial behavior of the two specimen configurations is the same until the knee load of the 1-2 specimen occurs. The 2-1 specimens failed at loads corresponding to the knee load of the 1-2 specimens. Figure 7 also shows that the initial stiffness of the 1-2 and 2-1 specimens is similar for the 90° loading angle despite a higher load carrying capacity of the 1-2 specimens.

Figure 5: Load vs. displacement curves for 1-2 Arcan specimens under monotonic tensile load

Figure 6: Load vs. displacement curves for 2-1 Arcan specimens under monotonic tensile load

Figure 7: Monotonic behavior of 1-2 and 2-1 specimens under shear load.

3.2 Fatigue Tests

The maximum cyclic load (P_{max}) for all load-controlled fatigue tests was selected near average ‘knee’ load for each specimen configuration and loading angle. Unless there was a runout, all fatigue tests were terminated when the instantaneous stiffness (load/displacement) became equal to half the stiffness at the end of the first 100 cycles.

The fatigue responses of the 1-2 and 2-1 Arcan specimens at various loading angles are shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9, respectively. For both specimen configurations, the fatigue performance was reduced with increasing loading angle. It is seen in Figure 8 that the fatigue performance of the material in the 1-2 configuration is much higher at lower loading angles of 30° and 45°. However, the difference in the fatigue performance of the material seems to become smaller at higher loading angles of 60° and 90°. This is primarily due to the fact that at higher loading angles, the shear stress component becomes higher than the normal stress component.

Unlike the 1-2 specimens, the fatigue response of the 2-1 specimens tend to become less sensitive to loading angle at loading angles of 45° and higher, as shown Figure 9. The 2-1 specimens were also tested at 0° loading angles and it is seen that the fatigue performance of the material in the 2-1 configuration is much higher than at 30° loading angle.

Both Figure 8 and Figure 9 show that the maximum cyclic load decreases with log (number of cycles to failure) so that the fatigue response in terms of the maximum cyclic load can be represented by the following equation:

$$P_{max} = A (\log_{10} N)^B \tag{1}$$

where, P_{max} is the maximum cyclic load, N is the number of cycles to failure, and A and B are constants. A is called the fatigue strength coefficient and B is the fatigue exponent. The A and B values for the both the test configurations are given in Table 4 and Table 5. Both A and B are reduced with increasing loading angle.

Loading Angle	A	B	R ²
0°	-	-	-
30°	25.975	-0.120	0.932
45°	10.658	-0.076	0.975
60°	9.3622	-0.091	0.955
90°	6.7524	-0.072	0.971

Table 4: Fatigue life equation parameters for 1-2 specimens

Loading Angle	A	B	R ²
0°	21.221	-0.104	0.959
30°	8.172	-0.079	0.965
45°	7.4257	-0.09	0.951
60°	7.5275	-0.098	0.947
90°	6.2862	-0.077	0.943

Table 5: Fatigue life equation parameters for 2-1 specimens

Figure 8: Fatigue tests results for 1-2 Arcan specimens at different loading angles
 (* Failure is defined as 50% decrease in stiffness at 100 cycles)

Figure 9: Fatigue tests results for 2-1 Arcan specimens at different loading angles
(* Failure is defined as 50% decrease in stiffness at 100 cycles)

The fatigue data are plotted in Figure 10 with the vertical axis representing the ratio of the maximum cyclic load and knee load. The fatigue response in terms of the maximum cyclic load can be represented by the following equation:

$$(P_{max})_{knee} = C (\log_{10} N)^D \quad (2)$$

where, $(P_{max})_{knee}$ is the maximum cyclic load expressed as a percentage of the knee load, N is the number of cycles to failure, and C and D are constants. The C and D values for the both the test configurations are given in Table 6 and Table 7. It is seen that as a percentage of the knee load, fatigue response of the 2-1 specimens is significantly higher than that of the 1-2 specimens. Within the 1-2 specimen category, fatigue response of the material is closer for a) 30° and 45° loading and b) 60° and 90° loading.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Fatigue response of a $[0/90/0_5/\bar{0}]_S$ E-glass laminate at various loading angles was determined using butterfly-shaped Arcan specimens. Two different specimen configurations were used, one with 0° fiber orientation in the outer layers and the other with 90° fiber orientation in the outer layers. The fatigue performance of 1-2 specimens with 0° fiber orientation in 87% of the layers was generally better than 2-1 specimens with 90° fiber orientation in 87% of the layers. However, when viewed as a percentage of the monotonic knee load, the fatigue response of the 2-1 specimens was better than 1-2 specimens. It is also observed that as the shear stress component is increased while the normal stress component is increased, the fatigue performance is decreased. Also, as the shear stress component increases relative to the normal stress component, the fatigue performance becomes closer.

Figure 10: Fatigue response (in terms of load ratio) of Arcan specimens

Loading Angle	C	D	R ²
30°	323.80	-0.120	0.932
45°	197.30	-0.076	0.975
60°	210.43	-0.091	0.955
90°	170.56	-0.072	0.971

Table 6: Fatigue life equation parameters for 1-2 specimens

Loading Angle	C	D	R ²
30°	296.30	-0.079	0.965
45°	301.24	-0.090	0.951
60°	308.38	-0.098	0.947
90°	283.80	-0.077	0.943

Table 7: Fatigue life equation parameters for 2-1 specimens

5 REFERENCES

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